

TEST RESULTS FOR PREDICTION OF COMPOSITE STRESSES AT SKIN-STIFFENER INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Advanced Composite Material was introduced in main components of civil aircraft in the early 80's with the development, certification and entrance in service of carbon fibre stabilizers in some of the Airbus models.

Typical configuration of these structures is a longitudinal and transverse stiffened skin. In order to make use of all structure load capability under compression and shear load it is allowed to work beyond buckling load. Under these conditions, most typical failure mode is skin-stiffener delamination or debonding.

In this report, test results of present aeronautical structures working in the postbuckling range and suitable to failure by delamination are presented. Stiffened panels have been tested under compression and shear load. The aim of these test results is to understand the occurrence of this type of failure and prevent it by means of a detailed design.

Keyword: delamination, debonding, buckling, postbuckling

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent specific properties of modulus and strength, Advanced Composite Materials are widely used in aeronautical industry.

Typical structure configuration of skin panels for a torque box is a thin skin with longitudinal and transversal stiffeners, figure 1. Main critical loads for these structures are compression and shear load, combined or not with internal fuel pressure. In order to take advantage of all load capability of the structure it may be useful to allow the panels work in the range, with the stiffener in its plane.

Both longitudinal and transversal stiffeners are cocured with the skin in one autoclave shot,

being the link between skin and stiffener a thin layer of resin or adhesive. In this resin layer, and specially near a free edge, as the stiffener flange end, interlaminar stresses due to in plane loads may appear.

With the structure working in the postbuckling range, skin deforms out of its plane, with the development of loads out of the panel plane. This type of load causes an increase of the interlaminar peeling and shear stresses at skin-stiffener interface. In this condition most typical failure mode is skin-stiffener delamination or debonding.

Figure 1. Structure configuration

Actually, the ultimate failure load for both types of load and the postbuckling capability is obtained by test. These test are very expensive and do not allow to check different design solutions due to the cost of a large number of tests. Therefore it is important to analyze the ultimate failure load from a theoretical point of view in order to check the influence of different design solutions in the structure behaviour.

With these two objectives, development of a theoretical failure criteria and to analyze the influence of design solutions, a test plan has been established, combining different structural configurations and loads.

This report presents these test results and a preliminary analysis. In addition, a correlation with finite element models is included.

2. STRUCTURE DESIGN

In a structure like that shown in figure 1, compression and tension load due to spanwise bending moment must be supported by stiffener and skin as a whole, meanwhile shear load due to torque moment is supported only by skin.

Then first structural requirement of skin laminate is shear stiffness. Lay-up of skin requires mainly $\pm 45^\circ$ layers, the amount of 0° layers should be lower than 20%. This skin lay-up has

a lower longitudinal stiffness and this must be compensated by the stiffeners. Stiffener lay-up requires no less than 60% of 0° layers. In these conditions axial load will be carried out mainly by stiffeners.

For the present test lay-up for longitudinal stiffeners is:

$$(+45/-45/0_3/90/0_3/90/0_3/-45/45)_s$$

Lay-up for transverse stiffeners is:

$$(+45/-45/-45/+45/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/+45/-45/-45/+45)_s$$

Two different thickness panels have been tested, in order to analyze its influence in the structure response:

$$(+45/-45/0/-45/45/90/-45/45/0/45/-45/90/45/-45/0/-45/45) \quad \text{thickness:3.06}$$

$$(+45/-45/0/-45/45/90/45/-45/0/-45/45) \quad \text{thickness:1.98}$$

Dimension of panels, skin and stiffeners have been selected according to actual aeronautical structures, taking into account mainly production requirements in order to avoid an excessively academic test. These values are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Specimen dimensions.

Material used for panel production is AS4/8552 with the following properties:

$$E_{xx} = 120000 \text{ MPa}$$

$$E_{yy} = 9000 \text{ MPa}$$

$$G_{xy} = 3700 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\nu_{xy} = 0.3$$

$$\text{layer nominal thickness} = 0.18 \text{ mm}$$

All specimens include artificial defects and impacts damages at critical locations in order to simulate in service conditions.

Two types of load will be used: compression and shear. Test matrix is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Test matrix

SKIN THICKNESS	LOAD TYPE	NUMBER OF SPECIMENS	DEFECTS IMPACTS	STRAIN GAUGES	ROSETTES
3.06	COMPRESSION	2	YES	24	8
3.06	SHEAR	2	YES	12	8
1.98	COMPRESSION	2	YES	24	8
1.98	SHEAR	2	YES	12	8

3. TEST RESULTS

During the test, the strains measured in different locations of the structure has been recorded. Selected locations are: middle point between longitudinal and transverse stiffener, at both skin surfaces, and longitudinal stiffener webs, also at both surfaces.

Table 2 summarizes the principal items of test results. Values shown in table 2 are average values among different strain gauges at equivalent locations of skin. Two examples of strain vs. load curve at the middle point of skin bay are shown in figures 3 and 4, for compression and shear load respectively. These figures include results for the thinner skin.

Table 2. Test results

SKIN THICKNESS	LOAD TYPE	BUCKLING MICROSTRAIN	POSTBUCKLING CAPABILITY
3.06	COMPRESSION	-3000	33 %
3.06	SHEAR	5616	11 %
1.98	COMPRESSION	-1956	78 %
1.98	SHEAR	2670	88 %

4. PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS AND F.E.M. CORRELATION

As expected, postbuckling capability increases with the panel width/panel thickness ratio, being the increment greater for shear load.

Failure is explosive for both types of load. For compression load test, mean strain between outer and inner surfaces remains constant after buckling. On the other hand, for shear load test, mean strain still grows after buckling, but with a lower stiffness.

For thicker skin panels no bending strain is presented before buckling. For the thinner ones small bending strain came up as shown on figures 3 and 4. It may be due to panel weaviness. That effect increases as panel thickness decrease.

Figure 3. Strain vs. Load. Compression load.

Figure 4. Strain vs. Load. Shear load.

Figure 5. Test correlation. Nonlinear analysis.

In order to obtain interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface a F.E.M test correlation have been performed. Firstly a linear static analysis is performed. Small differences between theoretical and test results are found, forcing the use of the actual stiffness properties of skin and stiffener. These elastic properties may be obtained from a flat laminate with same stacking sequence of specimen, cured at the same autoclave cycle and using the same batch of material.

After correlation of linear static response, a F.E.M. linear buckling analysis was performed. Differences between test and F.E.M. results are lower than 4%, using actual stiffness and an average skin thickness.

Next step in test correlation is a nonlinear analysis with F.E.M.. Figure 5 shows strain at two equivalent location on specimen and the F.E.M. results for a shear load test. There is a slight difference between test and F.E.M. results and this difference is due to the fact of small changes in panel thickness. F.E. analysis was performed with an average skin thickness.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Test results for present aeronautical structure working in the postbuckling range have been presented.

Preliminary analysis shows the expected influence of panel width/panel thickness ratio in the postbuckling capability of structure. This variation is greater for shear load.

In all cases delamination process is explosive.

Test correlation with F.E.M. is good if real elastic properties are used in linear analysis. For nonlinear analysis it is necessary to simulate the real panel surface and thickness.

After this preliminary correlation further detailed analysis will be developed in order to obtain interlaminar stresses at skin-stiffener interface.